

Redescription of the holotypes of *Tylosaurus proriger* and *Tylosaurus nepaeolicus* (Squamata: Mosasauridae) - Erratum

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ERRATUM

An unfortunate error occurred during the production stage in Table 2. Editors apologize for the inconvenience. The table should read as follows:

Measurement	<i>T. proriger</i> MCZ VPRA 4374	<i>T. nepaeolicus</i> AMNH FARB 1565
Body length	** 8.24 m	** 4.87 m
Skull length	* 1.09 m	* 0.63 m
Premaxilla rostrum length	5.5 cm	-
1 st -6 th maxilla teeth	25 cm	-
Quadrate height	** 14.1 cm	8.2 cm
Jaw length	* 1.14 m	* 0.68 m
Dentary length	65.8 cm	-
1 st -6 th dentary teeth	24 cm	-

Table 2. Select measurements and estimates of the holotype specimens, *Tylosaurus proriger* MCZ VPRA 4374 and *Tylosaurus nepaeolicus* AMNH FARB 1565. When both left and right bones are preserved, an average of the two is given. Estimates, explained in the text, are indicated by asterisks, and estimates calculated from other estimates are indicated by two asterisks.

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